

PARALLEL PROJECTION MATRIX IN COMPUTER VISUALIZATION

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Beknazarova Saida Safibullayevna

prof, d.t.s.

Anvarxo'jaev Sarvar A'zamxo'ja o'g'li

Magister

Tashkent University of Information Technologies named by Muhammad Al- Khwarizmi

Abstract: 3D graphics is an indispensable tool when it is necessary to demonstrate any complex technical nodes, multi-stage productions, architectural structures. Three-dimensionality clearly displays all the features of the structure of the object, its smallest elements, and parts of the structure of the structure hidden from the observer's eyes. Three-dimensional graphics are considered an indispensable tool for demonstrating various kinds of complex technical nodes, multi-stage productions, architectural structures. Three-dimensional models clearly show all the features of the structure of the object, its smallest elements that are hidden from the eyes of the observer. At the moment, 3D images are the peak of perfection in the advertising and design industry

Keywords: classical visualization, computer visualization, projective transformation.

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Despite the fact that parallel projection is a special case of perspective projection, we first consider the normalization technique with parallel orthogonal projection, and then extend it to perspective projection.

The projection process is divided into two parts: first, using a non-degenerate transformation in homogeneous coordinates, we transform the specified visibility zone into a standard one (normalization), and then we perform a projective transformation. At the first stage, objects are distorted in such a way that after performing a projective transformation of the selected type (orthogonal) in relation to these objects and the visibility zone at the second stage, we get.

$$x_p = x, y_p = y, z_p = 0$$

In fact, the orthogonal projective transformation is reduced to equating the z component to zero or to ignoring it, since it becomes unnecessary when displayed. Thus, the entire computational load is transferred to the first stage of the process. The separation of the projection process into two stages is largely related to other computer graphics tasks performed during conveyor processing. In particular, the clipping operation is performed when visualizing three-dimensional objects at several stages, and the use of non-degenerate transformation matrices allows you to save information about the depth of the location of objects along the projecting beam, which is later necessary to remove invisible surfaces and correctly paint over objects.

In OpenGL, there is a separation between screen coordinates, which are two-dimensional and do not contain depth information, and window coordinates,

which are three-dimensional and store depth information. The projection matrix and the subsequent perspective division transform the vertices into window coordinates.

The projection matrix is formed as a superposition of two affine transformations: shift and scaling. In orthogonal projection, the simplest area of visibility is a cube, the center of which is at the origin, and the faces are formed by planes

$$x = 1, x = -1, y = 1, y = -1, z = 1, z = -1$$

In OpenGL, such a visibility cube is set by the system by default. To force its installation, you need to include the following sequence of commands in the program:

```
glMatrixMode (GL_PROJECTION);
glLoadIdentity ();
glOrtho (-1.0, 1.0,-1.0, 1.0,-1.0, 1.0);
```

This cube is called the canonical visibility zone. The last two arguments in the `glOrtho()` call are the distance to the near and far clipping planes measured from the camera position in the direction of the negative semi-axis G . The front clipping plane $r = 1.0$ is behind the camera, the rear clipping plane $r = -1.0$ is in front of the camera, although the projecting rays are parallel and orthogonal projection is similar in its properties to using a telephoto lens with a very large focal length.

Suppose that when calling the `glOrtho()` function, arbitrary argument values are set:

```
glOrtho ( $x_{min}, x_{max}, y_{max}, y_{min}, l_{near}, l_{far}$ )
```

The matrix obtained in this way transforms the coordinates of the vertices describing the objects that were specified when calling `glVertex ()` into vertices inside the canonical visibility zone, for which scaling and shifting transformations are performed. As a result, those vertices that were inside the specified parallelepiped of visibility are transformed into vertices that are inside the canonical visibility zone, and those vertices that were outside of the specified parallelepiped of visibility will also be outside the canonical visibility zone.

So, the projection matrix is determined by the specified projection type and the visibility zone parameters passed as arguments to the `glOrtho()` function. The position and orientation of the camera are set by the view matrix. These two matrices – view and projection – are multiplied, and the coordinates of the points of the objects are multiplied on the right by the resulting matrix.

To output the orthogonal projection matrix, it is necessary to solve two problems: first, using the shift transformation, move the center of a given parallelepiped to the center of the canonical visibility zone – the origin of coordinates, then change the scale coefficients so that each edge of the parallelepiped has a length of 2 units.

$$T \left(-\frac{x_{max} + x_{min}}{2}, -\frac{y_{max} + y_{min}}{2}, -\frac{z_{max} + z_{min}}{2} \right)$$

$$S \left(\frac{2}{x_{max} - x_{min}}, \frac{2}{y_{max} - y_{min}}, \frac{2}{z_{max} - z_{min}} \right)$$

after the superposition of which the projection matrix is formed

$$P = ST \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{x_{max} - x_{min}} & 0 & 0 & -\frac{x_{max} + x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \\ 0 & \frac{2}{y_{max} - y_{min}} & 0 & -\frac{y_{max} + y_{min}}{y_{max} - y_{min}} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2}{z_{max} - z_{min}} & -\frac{z_{max} + z_{min}}{z_{max} - z_{min}} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Since the projection axis of the camera is directed along the negative half-axis z and the projecting rays are directed from the infinity of the negative half-space to the origin, then $z_{max} = l_{far}$ and $z_{min} = l_{near}$.

After calling the `glortho()` function, the projection matrix will take the following form:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{x_{max} - x_{min}} & 0 & 0 & -\frac{x_{max} + x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \\ 0 & \frac{2}{y_{max} - y_{min}} & 0 & -\frac{y_{max} + y_{min}}{y_{max} - y_{min}} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2}{l_{far} - l_{near}} & -\frac{l_{far} + l_{near}}{l_{far} - l_{near}} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Since projection modeling is a key task in three-dimensional computer graphics, it is impossible to write a good application program or develop a new graphics system without a deep understanding of the mathematical methods used in this process. Moreover, although the functions of working with projective transformations that are available in graphic libraries give quite satisfactory results in most situations that arise in the practice of developing graphic applications, some types of projections, in particular oblique, are most often not supported. If you need to organize such a projection in an application, you have to resort to indirect methods, and for this you need a deep understanding of the mechanisms of the system.

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